

“...BUT OF COURSE YOU ALREADY KNEW ABOUT ALL OF THIS...”

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A week after returning from [the yearly NVMO \(Netherlands/Flemish Society For Medical Education\) meeting](#), I'm still processing just how much there was to digest. The topic, planetary health in education, was close to my heart; the meeting was organized by my faculty, and for the first time in (ehm) possibly 20-ish years I made and presented a poster (Nordquist ea, 2026). The poster was unexpectedly great fun, I had forgotten how much interaction that brings; seeing the hard work my colleagues put into the conference working so well brought vicarious pride.

A snail reminder of both slow science, and taking your home with you wherever you go- even to Groningen for a conference

But in all honesty, the session that stayed with me the most this year was one where familiar projects were presented: I am familiar with [the projects that Marielle Jambroes and Eugenie Mac-Nac](#) run to connect future health care professionals with people living in neighbourhoods with poverty issues, and I am more than familiar with the [Zorg Gezondheid en Samenleving](#) (Care, Health and Society) bachelors as a member of the Education Advisory Committee. And yet: hearing colleagues tell the story from beginning to end, put these projects back into perspective for me.

How often do we hear about the things those our direct colleagues are working on in a coherent story, beginning to end, with all of the trials and tribulations in context? On reflecting I

realized.... Not that often. I hear the snippets of what has gone well, what hasn't, what is ongoing, and sometimes know where it all started, but not always. After the session as we all caught up a bit, when one of the speakers said "But of course you already knew about all of this"... I realized, I did and yet didn't. I knew all the pieces, but now I see the whole puzzle again.

During this same conference, which involved four 2-hour train trips Utrecht to Groningen (and back), I also worked my way through Isabella Stengers "Another Science is Possible- A Manifesto for Slow Science". One of the things she stresses, is the importance of conversations- though hers is more about the everyday snippets (which are also crucial), I am struck now by how important it is to take the time to listen to the whole story from colleagues. Sometimes we are too close to the mosaic to see the whole picture.

I return to work with the renewed inspiration and renewed awareness of how fortunate I am to work with such talented, dedicated and generally amazing people. Another science (and education) is indeed possible, and sometimes very close to home.

Nordquist, R. E., Deelen, E., Verweij, S., & Diemers, A. (2026). "*Hoe kunnen we straks goed voor dieren in armoede zorgen?*" *Mastersstudenten diergeneeskunde maken kennis met de invloed van armoede op veterinaire zorg*. Nederlands Vereniging Medisch Onderwijs Congres, Groningen, the Netherlands.

Stengers, Isabella. (2017). *Another Science is Possible: Manifesto for a Slow Science*. Polity Press. ISBN 9781509521814